

And Justice for All!
**The Contributions of the African Diaspora to the Enrichment of Critical Theory:
Postcolonial Theory and Critical Race Theory**

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Introduction

Problem Statement

In the 1960s, critical theory has swept the industrialized Western Europe. Critical theorists exposed and deconstructed the power of the dominant capitalist White male. However, a problem arises. Most of the authors were Judeo-Christian White Western European males. Other voices, especially those of people of color, including people of the African Diaspora, were still not heard. Critical theory is now mainstreamed as one of competing perspectives in the dominant discourses. However, critical writings by people of the African Diaspora are mainly tucked in Black Studies or suggested readings.

Research Goal and Questions

While reviewing the contributions of various authors to critical theory, this paper aims to highlight the voices of authors of the African Diaspora. The following are the research questions: What are the major characteristics and contributions of critical theory to theory building? What are the key features of the critical postcolonial theories of the African Diaspora in the Caribbean, Western Europe and the African Continent? What are the chief elements of the critical race theory of the African Diaspora in the U.S.?

Type of Research

This collaborative research is a critical survey of literature, quoting original sources as much as possible, in English and other languages, such as French. It discusses the contributions of the founders of critical theory. Beyond that, this research digs deeper by searching for critical theory beyond the hitherto marginalized but now mainstreamed theories of Judeo-Christian White men. In fact, it presents the views of people of the African Diaspora who have extended the dialogue and debate about human and social emancipation. For this purpose, this research presents an integrate review of literature stretching from traditional theory to critical theory, postcolonial theory, and critical race theory.

Findings

Critical Theory

Opposition to Traditional Theory. Taken loosely, critical theory refers to perspectives that critically view both human sciences in particular and society in general. Strictly speaking, though, critical theory refers to authors of the *Institut für Sozialforschung* (Institute for Social Research), originally based in Frankfurt; hence, it is also known as the “Frankfurt School.” While traditional theory is disinterested and therefore uncritical, critical theory is interested in

realizing radical social transformation for human emancipation. Horkheimer (1972, p. 210; 1976, p. 220) argued that critical theory aims to “transcend the tension and abolish the opposition between the individual’s purposefulness, spontaneity, and rationality,” as well as “those work-process relationships upon which the society is built.” Habermas (1990, p. 9) critiqued the “project of modernity” as based on “objective science, universal morality and law, and autonomous art according to their inner logic,” for “the rational organization of everyday social life.” Adorno and Horkheimer (1997) claimed that Enlightenment ideas repress and violate difference and otherness, asserting male domination over nature, human beings in general, and women in particular. Both Adorno and Horkheimer were opposed to Auguste Comte’s positivism—a form of empiricism—claiming that it does not realistically portray social realities. Horkheimer (1972, p. 183) is critical of blind obedience to “instrumental reason,” the scientific method and uncritical approval of empirical results, saying that “it is naïve and bigoted to think and speak only in the language of science,” rejecting rational science as the basis of valid knowledge on which arbitrary capitalism is constructed.

Concerned with a radical change of existing social set up, critical theory is opposed to the system-maintaining traditional uncritical theory. Adorno (2000, p. 176) said that there is “no ethics...in the administered world” and “the premise of ethics is the critique of the administered world.” Added Adorno (1974, p. 57): “People thinking in the forms of free, detached, disinterested appraisal were unable to accommodate...the...violence which in reality annuls such thinking.” Critical theorists envision a future society composed of free people, made possible with technical means already at hand. Marcuse (2002, p. xli) said that “specific possibilities exist for the amelioration of human life and specific ways and means of realizing these possibilities.”

Marxist Roots. Critical theory has its roots in Marx (1967, p. 217), who insisted that we must be critical, “not anticipate the world dogmatically” but be engaged in “*relentless criticism for all existing conditions*,” as well as not be “afraid of its findings” and “of conflict with the powers that be.” As a materialist, Marx turned idealist Hegelian philosophy upside down. In his *Contribution to the Critique of Hegel’s Philosophy of Right*, Marx (1994) explained that his criticism of Hegel’s philosophy of state and right is a critical analysis of the modern state and its reality. Traditional theory considers knowledge as neutral. However, critical theory argues that by treating knowledge as neutral, traditional theory is engaged in the reproduction of the economic structures and cultural hegemony of the dominant groups in the status quo. Marx & Engels (1967, p. 647) noted: “The philosophers have only *interpreted* the world in various ways; the point is to *change* it.” Marx and Engels, who were lifelong co-authors, developed their ontology based on dialectical historical materialism. In *A Reader in Marxist Philosophy*, Marx’ co-author Engels (1973, p. 204) wrote:

According to the materialist conception of history, the ultimately determining element in history is the production and reproduction of real life. More than this neither Marx nor I have ever asserted. Hence, if somebody twists this into saying that the economic element is the only determining one, he transforms that preposition into a meaningful, abstract, senseless phrase. The economic situation is the basis, but the various elements of the superstructure--...juristic, philosophical..., [and] religious views ...—also exercise their influence upon the course of the historical struggles and in many cases preponderate in determining their form. There is an interaction of all these elements in which, amid all the endless host of accidents..., the economic movement finally asserts itself as necessary.

Focus on the Superstructure. There are differences between classical Marxism and critical theory. Clearly, based on the foregoing quotation, classical Marxism identifies the world and existence as primary, independent of consciousness, which is derivative. However, classical Marxism clarifies that consciousness and the other elements of the superstructure can influence reality. However, critical theorists—and most people using critical theory after them—mistakenly claim that classical Marxism is economically deterministic, contrary to the original words of Engels cited above. For this reason, they wrongly believed that they have “rejected the economic determinism of orthodox Marxism,” which Marx and Engels never asserted, “yet carried on the Marxist tradition of critiquing society” (Griffin, 2003, p. 30). On the whole, critical theory is critique of ideology, which exposes and gives explanations for which people consent to representations that do not serve their objective interests but legitimize the dominant class in power. Both classical Marxists and critical theorists share a common focus on analyzing power, knowledge production, hegemony, oppression in society, and problems with capitalism. However, they differ in their ideas on how to bring about social change. Classical Marxists wage revolutionary and ideological struggles, while critical theorists seek to create a more participatory and democratic society. If classical Marxism dialectically upholds changing conditions as the basis of changing consciousness, critical theorists argue that restructuring society begins with a change in human consciousness, which turns classical Marxism upside down. Classical Marxists noted that Marcuse claimed that the source of “revolutionary transformation” is “man’s consciousness” or “man’s imagination” (Kirilenko & Korshunova, 1985, p. 50). Critical theorists emphasize the importance of human agency in changing social structures. Classical Marxists reject and seek to replace capitalism, while critical theorists accept capitalism as a fact of life.

Foucault (1980, p. 122) asserted that “the State consists in the codification of a whole number of power relations,” adding that “truth isn’t outside power or lacking power” (p. 131). Explaining that as culture is an industry, Adorno said that the capitalists administer the world where consciousness is manipulated. Adorno and Marcuse claimed that capitalists have ideological control over people’s emotions and needs and the latter are not cognizant of their exploitation and alienation. Horkheimer (1972) asserted that, in a capitalist society, the profit-seeking economic power holders do not respond to the real needs of the people but create false needs. Claiming that the mass media numbs sensitivity to repression, Adorno (1978, p. 245) observed that “the pre-formation of people’s minds has increased to a degree that” leaves no “room for an awareness of it” by “the people themselves.” Asserting that the dominant class controls language in order to perpetuate power imbalance, Marcuse (1976, pp. 310-311) said that “the meaning of words and ideas” are “established by the publicity of the powers that be, and verified in their practices.” Uncritical acceptance of the social order leads to legitimizing oppression, reinforcing the roles of the oppressed. According to Adorno (1978, p. 256), “the cross-section of attitudes represents, not an approximation to the truth, but a cross-section of social illusion.”

By dispelling the taken-for-granted ideological illusion, critical theory provides social agents an opportunity to be engaged in the “development” of a society based on self-determination and “freedom” (Marcuse, 1969, p. 3). For Habermas (1990), communicative process is the foundation for transformation. Marcuse (1978, p. 8) said that “aesthetic transformation” can be achieved through “a reshaping of language, perception, and

understanding” in order to “reveal the essence of... the repressed potentialities of” human beings “and nature.” For Marcuse (as cited in Bottomore, 1989, p. 38), the hope for social transformation springs from “the outcasts and outsiders, the exploited and persecuted of other races and colors, the unemployed and the unemployable.” When people’s consciousness is raised, they then use critical theory as a tool for action that promotes human and social liberation.

Postcolonial Theory

While the founders of critical theory have indeed advanced knowledge by challenging traditional theory, they only expressed the voices of Judeo-Christian White males. Postcolonial theory moved one step further by presenting voices of people of color as well. Postcolonial theorists are found in Africa, the Caribbean, West Asia (more commonly known as the Middle East), and Europe. While there are many more authors, only postcolonial theorists of the African Diaspora are presented here. Aside from English, they wrote in different languages.

Whereas critical theorists responded to the legacy of both traditional theory and classical Marxism, postcolonial theorists responded to lack of ability of heretofore existing theories to explain their social realities which lie outside of Europe. People of the African Diaspora face alienation under colonialism and have to face racism continually, as a result of which, they—along with others—have sparked the development of postcolonial studies. Questioning the inherent cultural bias in scientific research that devalues Black civilizations, Diop argued that archeological and anthropological evidence proved that “Ancient Egypt was a Negro civilization” (1974, p. xiv) and that “all races descended from the Black race, according to a filiation process that science will one day explain” (p. xv).

In response to French colonialism in Africa, Césaire (1972), Damas (1938), and Senghor (1967) appropriated a pejorative term and turned it into one of pride, *negritude*, which is a system of social and political thought, which seeks interaction with other cultures on equal footing. In *Discourse on Colonialism*, Césaire (1972, p. 26) criticized European and U.S. colonialism, racism, and decadence, exclaiming that “the barbarism of Western Europe” is “only surpassed...by the barbarism of the United States”. Referring to colonialism and post-colonialism, Nkrumah (1964, p. iv) talked about the “armed struggle...against the forces of reaction and counter-revolution,” saw the sharp “class struggle in Africa” and “exposed the close links between the interests of neo-colonialism and the indigenous bourgeoisie.” In *Black Skin, White Masks*, Fanon (1967a) recounted the impact of imperialism on the subjugated peoples. Fanon’s *Wretched of the Earth* (1967b), which chronicled the atrocities that French troops committed in Algeria, inspired movements for “national liberation” (pp. 196-197) against colonialism. Explaining the reason for which the colonized wage revolution against the violence of the colonizers, Fanon (1967b, p. 28) wrote: “Their first encounter was marked by violence,” adding that “the exploitation of the natives by the settler—was carried on by dint of a great array of bayonets and cannon.”

Critical Legal and Race Theory

Critical legal theory (CLS) and critical race theory (CRT) trace their roots to critical theory. Noted Crenshaw, Gotunda, Peller & Thomas (1995, p. 108):

Critical scholars derive their visions of legal ideology in part from the work on Antonio Gramsci, an Italian neo-Marxist theorist who developed an approach to understanding domination....In examining domination as a combination of physical coercion and ideological control, Gramsci articulates the concept of hegemony, the means by which a system of attitudes and beliefs, permeating both popular consciousness and the ideology of elites, reinforces existing social arrangements and convinces the dominated classes that the existing order is inevitable.

Critical legal theory extends the underlying thinking of critical theory based on the Frankfurt School to Legal Theory, while critical race theory is a racialized response to critical theory. Both CLS and CRT claim that law is not a neutral arbiter of contested issues in human relations.

Rather, law is inherently political (Crenshaw, Gotunda, Peller & Thomas, 1995, p. xvii):

The faith of liberal lawyers in the gradual reform of American law through the victory of the superior rationality of progressive ideas depended on a belief in the central ideological myth of the law/politics distinction, namely that legal institutions employ a rational, apolitical, and neutral discourse with which to mediate the exercise of social power.

While critical legal theory applies critical theory to law, critical race theory focuses on race. Critical race theory asserts that powerful interests in society oppress, but the oppression, as far as African-Americans are concerned, is based on centrality of white privilege.

The failure of the CLS scholars to address racism in their analysis also renders their critique of rights and their overall analysis of law in America incomplete. Specifically, this failure leads to inability to appreciate fully the transformative significance of the civil rights movement in mobilizing black Americans and generating new demands. Further, the failure to consider the reality of those most oppressed by American institutions means that the CLS account of the hegemonic nature of legal thought overlooks a crucial dimension of American life itself--the ideological role of racism itself" (p.110).

Both CLS and CRT claim that law is not a neutral arbiter of contested issues in human relations. Hermeneutically, the basic difference is that, on the one hand, critical legal theory maintains that U.S. law is in fact a political system of thought and action which is meant to protect the entrenched elite. On the other hand, critical race theory argues that U.S. law is in fact a system of protection of the centrality of white privilege which subjugates African-Americans to a dominant system of thought and action based on white privilege.

Conclusion

Summary

The construction of social theory has come a long way, thanks in part to the contributions of people of the African Diaspora. In opposition to traditional positivistic theory was born revolutionary Marxism. Not satisfied with both uncritical traditional theory and classical Marxism, critical theorists revised Marxism to meet the needs of advanced industrialized Western societies.

Implications to Theory and Practice

Critical theory has implications to educational practices. Educators need to learn to be aware of “the predominance of ideology in their everyday thoughts and actions and in the institutions of civil society” (Brookfield, 2001, pp. 20-21). This paper concludes that educators must discuss authors of the African Diaspora not only in Black Studies courses or just “suggested readings,” but also integrated and mainstreamed in all other areas of study. Blacks and non-Blacks would benefit reading them. In addition, instructors and learners must go beyond English and learn other languages, such as Swahili, Arabic, other African languages, French, and German, so that literature hitherto untapped can be read—and read in the original languages in which they were written.

References

- Adorno, T. (1974). *Minima moralia*. (E. F. N. Jeffcott, Trans.). London. Verso.
- Adorno, T. (1978). Sociology and empirical research. In P. Connerton, (Ed.), *Critical sociology* (pp.237-257). Middlesex, U.K.: Penguin.
- Adorno, T. (2000). *Problems of moral philosophy*. (R. Livingstone, Trans.). Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Adorno, T. & Horkheimer, M. (1997). *Dialectic of Enlightenment*. (J. Cumming, Trans.). New York: Continuum.
- Bottomore, T. (1989). *The Frankfurt school*. London: Tavistock Publications.
- Césaire, A. (1972). *Discourse on colonialism*. (J. Pinkham, Trans.). New York: Monthly Review Press.
- Crenshaw, K., Gotunda, N., Peller, G., & Thomas, K. (Eds.). (1995). *Critical race theory: The key writings that formed the movement*. New York: The New Press.
- Damas, L. G. (1938). *Retour de Guyane*. Paris: Gallimard.
- Diop, C.A. (1974). *The African origin of civilization: myth or reality*. (M. Cook, Trans.). New York: L. Hill.
- Diop, C. A. (1963). *The Cultural Unity of Black Africa: The Domains of Patriarchy and of Matriarchy in Classical Antiquity*. Chicago: Third World Press.
- Fanon, F. (1967a). *Black skin, white masks*. New York: Grove Press.
- Fanon, F. (1967b). *Wretched of the earth*. (C. Farrington, Trans.). Harmondsworth: Penguin.
- Foucault, M. (1980). *Power/knowledge*. (C. Gordon, L. Marshall, J. Mepham, & K. Soper, Trans.). New York: Pantheon Books.
- Gramsci, A. (1993). *Letters from prison*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Griffin, E. (2003). *A first look at communication theory*. (5th ed.). Boston: McGraw-Hill.
- Habermas, J. (1990). Modernity—An incomplete project. (S. Ben-Habib, Trans.). In H. Foster, (Ed.). *Postmodern culture* (pp. 3-15). London: Pluto Press.
- Horkheimer, M. (1972). *Critical theory: Selected essays*. (M. J. O’Connell, Trans.). New York: Herder & Herder.
- Horkheimer, M. (1976). Traditional and critical theory. In P. Connerton, (Ed.), *Critical sociology* (pp.206-224). Middlesex, U.K.: Penguin.
- Marcuse, H. (1969). *Essays on Liberation*. Boston: Beacon.

- Marcuse, H. (1976). Repressive tolerance. In P. Connerton, (Ed.), *Critical sociology* (pp. 301-329). Middlesex, U.K.: Penguin.
- Marcuse, H. (1978). *The aesthetic dimension: Toward a Marxist critique of aesthetics*. Boston: Beacon Press.
- Marcuse, H. (2002). *One-dimensional man: Studies in ideology of advanced industrial society* (2nd ed.). New York: Routledge.
- Marx, K. (1967). *Writings of the young Marx on philosophy and society*. (L. D. Easton & K. H. Guddat, Trans.). New York: Anchor Books.
- Marx, K. (1994). *Karl Marx: Selected writings*. Indianapolis: Hackett Publishing Company, Inc.
- Marx, K., Engels, F. & Lenin, V. (1973). *A reader in Marxist philosophy*. H. Selsam & H. Martel, (Eds.). New York: International Publishers.
- Nkrumah, K. (1964). *Consciencism: Philosophy and ideology for decolonization*. New York: Monthly Review Press.
- Senghor, L. S. (1967). *Fondements de l'africanité ou Négritude et arabité*. Paris: Présence africaine.